

Data publication – policies and procedures from the PREPARDE project

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#preparde

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Why cite and publish data?

- **Pressure** from (UK) **government** to make data from publicly funded research available for free.
 - Scientists want attribution and credit for their work
 - Public want to know what the scientists are doing
- Research **funders** want reassurance that they're getting **value for money**
 - Relies on peer-review of science publications (well established) and data (not done yet!)
- Allows the wider **research community** to **find and use** datasets, and understand the **quality** of the data
- Extra **incentive** for scientists to submit their data to data centres in appropriate formats and with full metadata

<http://www.evidencebased-management.com/blog/2011/11/04/new-evidence-on-big-bonuses/>

PREPARDE: Peer REview for Publication & Accreditation of Research Data in the Earth sciences

- **Lead Institution:** University of Leicester
- **Partners**
 - British Atmospheric Data Centre (BADC)
 - US National Centre for Atmospheric Research (NCAR)
 - California Digital Library (CDL)
 - Digital Curation Centre (DCC)
 - University of Reading
 - Wiley-Blackwell
 - Faculty of 1000 Ltd
- **Project Lead:** Dr Jonathan Tedds (University of Leicester, jat26@le.ac.uk)
- **Project Manager:** Dr Sarah Callaghan (BADC, sarah.callaghan@stfc.ac.uk)
- **Length of Project:** 12 months
- **Project Start Date:** 1st July 2012
- **Project End Date:** 31st June 2013

Geoscience Data Journal, Wiley-Blackwell and the Royal Meteorological Society

- Partnership formed between **Royal Meteorological Society** and academic publishers **Wiley Blackwell** to develop a mechanism for the formal publication of data in the **Open Access Geoscience Data Journal**
- GDJ publishes short data articles **cross-linked** to, and **citing**, datasets that have been deposited in **approved** data centres and awarded DOIs (or other permanent identifier).
- A **data article describes a dataset**, giving details of its collection, processing, software, file formats, etc., without the requirement of novel analyses or ground breaking conclusions.
 - the **when, how and why** data was collected and what the data-product is.

How we publish data

The traditional online journal model

Overlay journal model for publishing data

PREPARDE topics

Example steps/workflow required for a researcher to publish a data paper

3 main areas of interest (in orange)

1. Workflows and cross-linking between journal and repository
2. Repository accreditation
3. Scientific peer-review of data

- Division of area of responsibilities between
 - *repository controlled* processes
 - *journal controlled* processes

Data repository workflows

- Data centre and journal workflows captured
 - Workflows are very varied! No one-size fits all method
 - Can have multiple workflows in the same data centre, depending on interactions with external sources (“Engaged submitter”/ “Data dumper” / “Third party requester”)

Repository Workflow – NCAR Comp. & Info. Systems Lab Research Data Archive (RDA)

Geoscience Data Journal Data Paper workflow

Journal workflow

Aim is to minimise effort needed to submit a data paper by taking advantage of already submitted metadata.

Sharing metadata also ensures that additions/corrections made in one location get propagated through to the others

Cross-linking

This is what we have to focus on for PREPARDE – demonstrate cross linking between GDJ and a data repository (BADC/NCAR)

Unfortunately this direct cross-linking isn't scaleable!

Need for off-the shelf solutions that can work across multiple research domains

What PREPARDE has done

- We already have a link from the GDJ data article to the data repository – thanks to the DOI.
- GDJ can also pull the standard DOI metadata attached to that DOI from the DataCite metadata store
- GDJ needs to inform the repository that their dataset has been cited/published – bearing in mind scaling issues!
- At this time, we have a manual work-around (i.e. email)
- ***Workshop on cross-linking between data centres and publishers 30th April 2013 at RAL, UK***

The GBS dataset: measure x

onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/gdj3.2/full

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Data Paper

The GBS dataset: measurements of satellite site diversity at 20.7 GHz in the UK

S. A. Callaghan, J. Waight, J. L. Agnew, C. J. Walden, C. L. Wrench, S. Ventouras

Issue

Article first published online: 17 MAR 2013
DOI: 10.1002/gdj3.2

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The research presented in this paper was funded by the UK's Ofcom as part of the Spectrum Efficiency Scheme and the support of Ofcom in providing the funding for the GBS experiment is greatly appreciated.

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Keywords:
site diversity; radio propagation; fade mitigation techniques

Abstract

The GBS (Global Broadcast Service) dataset is a series of radio attenuation measurements made at three sites in the UK: Chilbolton and Sparsholt, both in southern UK, and Dundee in Scotland. The aim of the experiment was to make long term measurements of the signal strength received from a 20.7 GHz beacon on the US Department of Defense satellite UFO-9 at multiple sites, in order to determine whether the use of site diversity as a fade mitigation technique would be effective. The dataset spans a period of 3 years, from August 2003 to August 2006 with signal attenuation sampled once per second.

Dataset

The GBS (Global Broadcast Service) dataset comes as 3 separate data streams:

- Identifier: doi:10.5285/639A3714-BC74-46A6-9026-64931F355E07
Creator: Science and Technology Facilities Council (STFC), Chilbolton Facility for Atmospheric and Radio Research, [Callaghan, S. A., J. Waight, C. J. Walden, J. Agnew and S. Ventouras].
Title: GBS 20.7 GHz slant path radio propagation measurements, Chilbolton site
publisher: NERC British Atmospheric Data Centre
Publication year: 2009
Resource type: Metadata document
Version: 1.0
- Identifier: doi:10.5285/db8d8981-1a51-4d6e-81c0-cced9b921390
Creator: Science and Technology Facilities Council (STFC), Chilbolton Facility for Atmospheric and Radio Research, [Callaghan, S. A., J. Waight, C. J. Walden, J. Agnew and S. Ventouras].

Live Data paper!

Dataset citation is first thing in the paper (after abstract) and is also included in reference list (to take advantage of citation count systems)

DOI: 10.1002/gdj3.2

Viewing GBS 20.7GHz slant x

badc.nerc.ac.uk/view/badc.nerc.ac.uk_ATOM_dep_11902119479621181

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GBS 20.7GHz slant path radio propagation measurements, Chilbolton site

General Info

Title: GBS 20.7GHz slant path radio propagation measurements, Chilbolton site
Type: Activity
Sub-Type: Deployment
Publication State: Citable
URI: http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/view/badc.nerc.ac.uk_ATOM_dep_11902119479621181

Summary

The GBS (Global Broadcast Service) dataset is a series of radio attenuation measurements made at three sites in the UK: Chilbolton and Sparsholt, both in southern UK, and Dundee in Scotland. The aim of the experiment was to make long term measurements of the signal strength received from a 20.7GHz beacon on the US Department of Defense satellite UFO-9 at multiple sites, in order to determine whether the use of site diversity as a fade mitigation technique would be effective. The dataset spans a period of 3 years, from August 2003 to August 2006 with signal attenuation sampled once per second.

Please cite this dataset as:
 Science and Technology Facilities Council (STFC), Chilbolton Facility for Atmospheric and Radio Research, [S. A. Callaghan, J. Waight, C. J. Walden, J. Agnew and S. Ventouras], GBS 20.7GHz slant path radio propagation measurements, Sparsholt site, [Internet]. British Atmospheric Data Centre, 2003-2005. 1st April 2014. doi:10.1002/gdj3.2

This dataset is cited in:
 S. A. Callaghan, J. Waight, J.L.Agnew, C. J. Walden, C.L.Wrench , S. Ventouras "The GBS dataset: measurements of satellite site diversity at 20.7 GHz in the UK", Geoscience Data Journal, 17 March 2013, DOI: 10.1002/gdj3.2

Author

Name email
 Science and Technology Facilities Council (STFC), Chilbolton Facility for Atmospheric and Radio Research, [S. A. Callaghan, J. Waight, C. J. Walden, J. Agnew and S. Ventouras]

Online References

Relation	Title
Apply for access	Apply for to GBS data from Chilbolton
Download	Data directory for GBS data from Chilbolton
Documentation	DOI for dataset:10.5285/620-2714-b71-46-c-0006-64021f355e07
Documentation	Data article in Geoscience Data Journal doi:10.1002/gdj3.2

Associated Data

Type	Title
Data Production Tool	Chilbolton: GBS receiver
Activity	Chilbolton Facility for Atmospheric and Radio Research (CFARR)
Observation Station	Chilbolton Facility for Atmospheric and Radio Research (CFARR), UK

Dataset catalogue page (and DOI landing page)

Reference to Data Article

Clickable link to Data Article

Repository accreditation

Link between data paper and dataset is crucial!

- How do data journal editors know a repository is trustworthy?
- How can repositories prove they're trustworthy?

What makes a repository trustworthy?

- Many things: mission, processes, expertise, workflows, history, systems, documentation, ...
- Assessing trustworthiness requires assessing the entire repository workflow
- ***PREPARDE / IDCC13 Workshop – report in draft***
- Peer review of data is implicitly peer review of repository

And what does “trustworthy” mean, when you get right down to it?

Repository accreditation schemes:

These schemes look at all of the business of running a repository, but don't directly address the issues required for data publication.

Data for publication needs to:

- Be persistent
- Be permanently identified
- Be provided with a landing page
- Have standard publication metadata
- Have accessibility/licensing information

Document at: <http://bit.ly/ZhYHZ1>
 Feedback to: <https://www.jiscmail.ac.uk/DATA-PUBLICATION>

Peer-review of data

Summary Recommendations from Workshop at the British Library, 11 March 2013.

Workshop attendees included funders, publishers, repository managers and other interested parties.

Draft recommendations put up for discussion and feedback from audience captured.

3 main parts to recommendations:

- Connecting data review with data management planning
- Connecting scientific, technical review and curation
- Connecting data review with article review

Feedback from the community still welcome!

Most scientists regarded the new streamlined peer-review process as 'quite an improvement.'

<http://libguides.luc.edu/content.php?pid=5464&sid=164619>

Document at: <http://bit.ly/DataPRforComment>

Feedback to: <https://www.iiscmail.ac.uk/DATA-PUBLICATION>

Please! Tell us what you think

Always happy to get input from others!

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Workshop on cross-linking between data centres and publishers 30th April 2013 at Rutherford Appleton Laboratory, UK

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